

The Austrian Real-World Laboratories - How to manage multi-stakeholder engagement in the wide field of mobility research

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Abstract

Pursued by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology, the Urban Mobility Lab (UML) initiative was created in order to complement mobility research with a Living Lab support structure to bring findings of research and development into real-life practice. Regarding the Sustainable development goals the laboratories help facilitating sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11) and foster innovation (SDG9) in the field of mobility. Five Urban Mobility Labs are funded and supported for four years, starting in 2017. Each UML has a specific regional trait - from a port area, to a city district to whole cities and their surroundings. Topics covered by the UMLs range from active mobility, passenger mobility, to freight transport. The support of open innovation in a mobility living lab with a range of services and thereby speeding up the innovation process requires the exchange and coordination of multi- actor cooperation frameworks. The Urban Mobility Labs bring together stakeholders from all different levels starting from the user level to regional and national policy level. The close collaboration with local, regional and national authorities to provide real-life test environments as well as to strategically steer and embed projects in fast track innovation is one of the unique selling points of the laboratories.

Keywords: *living labs, mobility labs, co-creation, stakeholder engagement, public partnerships, test environments*

1 Introduction

Current transport challenges require innovative solutions as the demand is constantly changing in terms of technological developments, organizational and legal aspects in the society. Research often fails when it comes to putting their concepts into practice. This is due lack of knowledge, acceptance, as well as embedding in specific regional contexts and missing transition processes established. The mobility sector in general is characterised by shared governance approaches, leading to a wide distribution of tasks between public, semi- public and private actors, which poses a significant challenge to bring research and development projects into real-life application. Therefore, the UML in their mission to support innovation projects and bridging the gap towards implementation need to pursue a multi-stakeholder approach in order to provide and integrate all ideas, requirements and framework conditions in a timely manner.

Pursued by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology, the Urban Mobility Lab (UML) initiative was created in order to complement mobility research and innovation activities in Austria in this sense. During a first exploration phase eight feasibility projects covering a variety of mobility topics had the chance to gain practical experience and deliberately test different approaches to generate a broad range of experiences and insights for a potential Urban Mobility Lab in the respective region. An accompanying study collected the different experiences from the exploration-phase-projects and fed them into a structured pool of knowledge.

Figure 1. Austrian Mobility Labs (own representation)

Subsequently five Urban Mobility Labs were chosen for an implementation phase funded for four years starting in 2017. A perspective of 10 years in operational terms was required for each UML. Currently the UMLs are establishing real-world laboratories in five different Austrian locations comprising districts, cities and regions. Each laboratory sets several thematic foci (outlined in figure 1), aiming to facilitate research projects in those fields by speeding up the implementation process. The UMLs provide a toolkit of services to accompany research projects during the innovation process and enhance their impact. As the concept of open innovation is a core element of the living labs, a broad integration of diverse stakeholder and users is strongly required.

The facilitation of an exchange and the coordination of multi-actor and multi-stakeholder frameworks are therefore pursued. The Urban Mobility Labs bring together stakeholders from different levels starting from the user level, to research, enterprises and to public policy level. The close collaboration with local, regional and national authorities allows strategic embedding and real-life testing of innovation projects embedded in the UML/Living Lab environment. This allows bringing research faster to implementation by providing test infrastructure not only in private surroundings, but also in public space.

This paper sets a focus on the development and continuity of a successful multi-stakeholder network in the field of mobility living labs with a special focus on integration of public authorities and how to facilitate collaboration between all types of stakeholders.

2 Organisational structure

The stakeholder involvement within the Urban Mobility Labs comprises different levels of integration. They depict the intensity of cooperation, ranging from core team, close partners to further contacts in UML-related fields and sectors.

Operative level

- Management team
- Core team

Strategic level

- Steering Committee
- Advisory Board

Additional contacts

- Further not formally established contacts
- Funding bodies

User level

- User groups

Figure 2. Organisational structure of the Urban Mobility Labs (own representation)

As shown in Figure 2 on the operational level the management team is the core of the Urban Mobility Labs and responsible for the coordination of all living lab activities including the establishment and further development of a knowledge hub, open innovation methods as well as services for research and development projects. This organisational part is mostly covered by a management team from one institution. The core team includes additional partners establishing the content of the UML. On this level a variety of institutions closely work together in each lab, taking over various responsibilities or work packages. The composition differs between the labs, as they are facing different challenges regarding research topics and regional traits and requirements. Partners within the teams of the UMLs are:

- Research institutions
- Universities and colleges
- Public transport providers
- Public authorities
- Private companies
- Service provider
- Public consulting firms
- Further partner

On a strategic level most UML include a steering committee that provide important inputs regarding the embedding of the UMLs and their supported project in regional and national strategies. The organisation of the knowledge exchange differs, but usually takes place on a regular basis. Additionally, further advisors including interest groups, experts, research etc. can give important inputs on this level and are addressed in regular joint meetings or one-to-one contacts.

Further stakeholders are activated to complement the UML team in order to e.g. bring in additional knowledge, provide further test environments or support in the transfer of the outcomes. The collaboration is usually based on a Letter Of Interest (LOI). Further contacts include a variety of stakeholders such as user groups or interest groups. Funding bodies, notably the Austrian Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology, enable the implementation of the Urban Mobility Labs facilitating the first phase till the labs can work in a cost- covering manner.

As an example, the UML Salzburg's organisational structure consists of an operative and a strategic level. On the operative level a core group is composed of one main management institution, the SIR Salzburg Research, which is responsible for the organisational aspects and further institutions, including public authorities and research companies/institutes, which offer functional and thematic input. The strategic level includes a steering group consisting of the same institutions as the core team overlooking the compliance of policy goals, as well as an advisory committee comprising representatives of the federation of regional industry, research, interest groups, political stakeholders, administration and further stakeholders. (Salzburger Institut für Raumordnung und Wohnen, 2018)

Partner and stakeholder environment

As shown in Figure 2 the labs cannot cover all the services that may be needed to support research projects along the full innovation cycle and to build up a laboratory structure in the field of mobility. Therefore, stakeholders are a crucial part of the Mobility Lab community. This is applicable to the structure of all five Urban Mobility Labs. The co-operation can either be formally prepared by a Letter Of Interest (LOI) or in a non- formal manner e.g. via different communication channels such as newsletters and mailing lists. The degree of integration into the UML can vary depending on the nature of cooperation. (Salzburger Institut für Raumordnung und Wohnen, 2018).

Figure 3. Partner network of the Urban Mobility Labs
(own representation)

The networks of the Urban Mobility Labs comprise a variety of stakeholders. They are still growing and developing constantly. Figure 4 gives an oversight of the current stakeholder groups involved in the five Urban Mobility Labs in Austria.

A strong network within the **research community**, including small research institutions, offers access to a comprehensive pool of knowledge as well as the possibility to jointly elaborate new research and innovation projects. Additionally, this stakeholder group presents the main body submitting research projects that presumably will be embedded in the UML structures.

Economic and industrial businesses can be valuable partners within research

projects by contributing an implementation-oriented view point. In many cases those projects do not only focus on the prototyping and implementation phase, but also the adaption of products on the market. Another important aspect of the cooperation is the provision of infrastructure and real-life test environments. **Small businesses and start-ups** are a specific group as they are especially flexible and innovation oriented. They are usually part of innovative projects using the UML structures.

Regarding real-life test environments the Urban Mobility Labs are trying to provide private as well as public space covering various traffic situations. Hence, they are closely working together with partners offering different environments covering testing areas such as for private commute and freight mobility solutions. Private partners providing their infrastructure to specific laboratories within the initiative are for example the Chemistry Park in Linz through the MobiLab OÖ and the Harbour Vienna through Thinkport VIENNA (FH OÖ Forschungs & Entwicklungs GmbH, 2018) (Universität für Bodenkultur Wien, 2018). Further on, **Mobility service providers** are important partners when it comes to test environments. They can offer possibilities for testing within the regular service framework or with additional infrastructure. They often work closely with cities and regional authorities. This can be an advantage, as some solutions need special permits.

One specific asset of the Urban Mobility Labs thereby is the strong direct collaboration with **public authorities**. The need for innovation can directly be passed on to the research community responding creating new projects meeting the demand. Solutions and approaches potentially contribute to the regional and national mobility goals. The Urban Mobility Labs can function as a bridge between different stakeholders. This is also important when it comes to providing test environments in public space. The Urban Mobility Labs are developing standardised steps to simplify the process of getting necessary approvals from the different stakeholders.

In the sense of open innovation within the living labs it is also important to integrate **user groups** and **interest groups** to enable sustainable research and to integrate user needs in an early stage of the innovation cycle. The laboratories aim to include users as innovators through co-creational methods.

2 Stakeholder Engagement Strategies

The development of a stakeholder network requires different methods targeting the specific groups mentioned in point 2. On the one hand the UMLs want to raise their awareness addressing stakeholder groups interested in embedding their research projects and using the services of the laboratories. On the other hand, the UMLs need

to build up a network of stakeholder which is needed to create a successful living lab environment. Therefore, each lab started with a bundle of measures to gain awareness in their region and overall in Austria. Till now a wide range of communication channels were introduced to address target groups (see Table 1).

To promote their laboratories each lab established a web presence including at least a web page showing general information about the lab, embedded projects, events, updates, contact information and their service portfolio. Some of the UMLs send out newsletter and set up additional profiles on social media channels. Furthermore, the UMLs created different promotion materials, mostly used on site, at events and exhibitions. Media presence can improve the publicity of the UML, it is especially important at relevant events and milestones. Press conferences were held by some UML at the early stage as an official start of the lab.

To gain awareness within the stakeholder community, the participation in events and conferences is an important activity. The labs do not only attend but also try to take an active part by submitting papers, present their work, offer workshops or take a stand in an exhibition often collaboratively with other Urban Mobility Labs. As an example, the MobiLab OÖ and other UMLs went one step further and applied for a membership within the EnoLL community (FH OÖ Forschungs & Entwicklungs GmbH, 2018).

Another measure to exchange knowledge and make new contacts is a study visit. The laboratories organise excursions to meet with other living labs or other relevant institutions that represent important contacts. The UMLs also coordinate networking events for their (LOI) stakeholders often targeting a specific topic.

To reach a broader audience and gain new contacts, the UMLs offer a variety of networking events. As each UML is focussing on specific mobility topics and offer diverse services, the direction and format of the happenings differs. As most events can be of interest to one or more groups of stakeholders the events strongly rely on collaborative methods. Examples will be described in chapter 4.

Access to test persons/users is a specific challenge to the UML as the integration of users is an important open innovation aspect. On the one hand the labs contact this stakeholder group on site offering specially designed events. The Aspern.mobil LAB focusses for example especially on a neighbourhood level concentrating strongly on user integration (Technische Universität Wien, 2018). Therefore, it offers **regular events in the district** to build up a community for co-creational method and enabling the citizens to take an active part in the innovative development of their surroundings. On the other hand, some UMLs have access to data bases. The UML Salzburg offers a possibility through a data base involving key actors that have access to test persons (Salzburger Institut für Raumordnung und Wohnen, 2018).

Table 1. Communication Channels

Urban Mobility Lab Network

Communication Channel	Description
Web Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webpage • Newsletter • Twitter • Facebook
Promotional material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Sticker • Brochures • Roll Ups • Goodies
<i>Press and Media</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press conference • Articles • Interviews • TV appearances
Community Network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in events and conferences • Presentations and workshops at events and conferences • Publications • Memberships in living lab communities e.g. EnoLL • Study tours • Events for LOI stakeholder
Network Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in public events • Events organised by the UML <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Informative Events ▪ Workshops ▪ Lectures and discussion rounds ▪ Events targeting a specific topic ▪ Networking dialogues
<i>Further Channels: (details see 3.2)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University courses • Personal contact • Advisory meetings (see 2.) • Meeting places, display rooms, etc. • Competitions and ideation challenges • Mobile laboratory facilities • Open innovation platforms • User panels • Hackathon with students

The Urban Mobility Lab initiative is accompanied by a so-called national contact point at the AustriaTech (an agency of the Austrian Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology -bmvit) which beside supporting the implementation phase of the laboratories and the networking among each other, also represents a contact point

for information about the initiative and further ongoing activities of the Urban Mobility Labs. This creates a link between all five Urban Mobility Labs in Austria and upcoming Mobility Lab initiatives. The Urban Mobility Lab network is publicly represented by a joint website. The contact point activates and coordinates submissions of technical and scientific papers, presentations and expo stands at several conferences each year. Furthermore, special match making events are organized bringing the laboratories together with Austrian research projects with a potential to be embedded in the UMLs. A special focus is set on research projects funded by the bmvit in order to enhance the efficiency of national innovation projects and to speed up the implementation process.

The supporting structure does not only aim to promote the initiative, but also to accelerate the knowledge exchange between the Mobility Labs in Austria and further laboratories. In addition, experts are invited on a regular basis providing knowledge required such as insights into the development of user panels and data management.

Table 2. Supporting elements within the UML initiative

Supporting elements	Description
Promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austrian Mobility Labs homepage • UML promotion material
Contact Point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing information regarding the initiative • UML hub
Networking Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network meeting of the UMLs • Knowledge exchange between the UMLs • Involvement of external experts and other living labs for joint learning
Conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective participation and presentation at conferences and other events • Joint exhibitions at conferences and other events
Study visits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective study visits
Match Making Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special events to bring together the UMLs and Austrian research projects
Funding calls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special funding pool or preferential treatment for research projects embedded in UML structures • Participation of the UMLs at kick off events

Collaborative methods

A basic service of the Urban Mobility Labs is to bring stakeholders together. Besides the support of knowledge and contact exchange, the main goal is to facilitate new research projects to be embedded into the laboratories. As a result, a variety of co-creational methods, applied in workshops and further innovative formats were developed by the UML. The following list shows examples offered by the UMLs.

- **Interactive Workshops** focussing on co-creation methods such as (speed) design thinking, design games, ideation workshops and cultural probe are offered by the UML in all stages of the innovation cycle. The further development of the offered methods is an important part of the UMLs work;
- Two UMLs offer **mobile laboratories** which can be built up wherever they are needed offering space and equipment for co-creation in the field;
- By close collaboration with public authorities and private companies, **test environments** can be offered to test prototypes in a real-life setting;
- Thinkport VIENNA offers a **display room** and two **start-up offices**, complemented by several events with relevant stakeholders in the field of freight transport. They also have an annual Forum called “Forum Green Logistics”. (Universität für Bodenkultur Wien, 2018);
- The **dissemination** of projects and results through the communication channels of the UML and specific stakeholder events offer a possibility to attract stakeholder to collaborate within the research project;
- Some of the laboratories organise **ideation workshops and challenges**. As an example, the MOBILITY LAB in Graz started a challenge looking for creative mobility solution for the city region. The best projects will be accompanied through the whole development process up until implementation. (Holding Graz, 2018);
- Several universities and technical colleges are involved in the UMLs; they started to offer **courses and lectures** to students working closely together with the laboratories. The Aspern.mobil LAB also organised a **hackathon** for students. (Technische Universität Wien, 2018);
- The UML Salzburg provides an **open innovation platform** as a design and information hub for the region offering organized information about (technical) services, documents and further data. (Salzburger Institut für Raumordnung und Wohnen, 2018);
- **Thematic excursions** are offered for example by Aspern.mobil LAB to show and analyse mobility infrastructure and public space to a variety of stakeholder groups. (Technische Universität Wien, 2018);
- **Technical tools** are offered to simplify the integration of test persons. One example is the PT feedback app offered by the UML Salzburg as a planning tool which enables users to comment on used services.

3 Prospective Development and Future Vision

The wide spectrum of the transport community poses a great challenge regarding the stakeholder engagement with the Urban Mobility Labs. It demands a transdisciplinary approach elaborating different formats to address stakeholders for the laboratories. In the frame of the support process provided by AustriaTech and the bmvit the UMLs can exchange knowledge, learn from each other and work together if considered beneficial. While UMLs share same challenges in terms of operating and supplying living lab support structures, each UML also has specific characteristics in terms of stakeholders and topics addressed. Therefore, the UMLs are trying to choose engagement strategies suitable for their objectives. Each lab is called to monitor and evaluate their implementation works and process towards the achievement of their goals. Additionally, there will be a joint evaluation process conducted by an independent party in 2020.

The support process provided to the UMLs creates a link between the laboratories enabling them not only to represent their respective lab individually but to raise awareness collaboratively. This joint network of the UML initiative is constantly growing. National and international interested parties are contacting the UML contact point to meet and collaborate with the labs. The UML initiative seems to create interest, but there are still a lot of stakeholders which need to be addressed specifically as the application of the living lab approach in urban mobility is relatively new. The experiences indicate that a basic understanding of the Urban Mobility Labs needs to be created.

While on UML level the development of a general stakeholder network is in progress, further effort will be needed to establish and enlarge a specific stakeholder network needed for targeted support of already embedded and future research and development projects. The integration of the UMLs as a necessary or recommended partner in the Austrian funding calls of the programme “Mobility of the Future” is an important support element to encourage projects to make use of UML services. One objective is to make the laboratories more tangible by showing the collaboration between the research projects and the UML making the initiative more attractive for future research and stakeholder engagement.

The salient asset of the UMLs for R&D projects which is often emphasised but maybe not fully perceived yet is the close working relationship with public authorities. The laboratories are still setting up the details of the services which can be offered as a result of the cooperation. Integrating public authorities as stakeholders of the UMLs might be a complex issue to varying policy goals, hierarchies and differing responsibilities, but can be of mutual benefit by bringing mobility solutions responding to actual needs into cities and open up planning process for disruptive innovations.

Looking into the future it will be important to further support the UML initiative and the knowledge and experience exchange within Austria, Europe and beyond. This allows the laboratories to improve management and stakeholder engagement and to further develop the living lab approach for mobility challenges

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